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Research Article

**A DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH TO ASSESS OCCURRENCE OF
HYPONATREMIA INDUCED BY TERLIPRESSIN AMONG
ACUTE VARICEAL BLEEDING PATIENTS**¹Dr. Ayesha Ejaz, ²Dr. Umair Atta, ³Dr. Aisha Naveed¹Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore, ²Basic Health Unit Dumbar Tribal Area, ³Nishtar Medical College

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Abstract:

Objective: The objective of this research was to assess hyponatremia induced Terlipressin among acute variceal bleeding patients.

Materials & Methods: This descriptive research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from July 2017 to March 2018 on a total of one hundred patients who were presented with acute variceal bleeding. All the patients were Hyponatremia induced Terlipressin were also examined. All the patients faced the onset of acute variceal bleeding because of portal hypertension who were in the age bracket of (20 – 60) years from both genders. We did not include all those patients who presented hepatocellular carcinoma, hyponatremia, hypothyroidism, nephritic syndrome, Addison disease, severe diarrhoea, renal failure, cardiovascular disease, levels of serum sodium (≤ 135 mEq/L), hypersensitive patients, pregnant patients and unwilling patients.

Results: The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of (20 – 60) years and the mean age of these patients was (45.78 ± 8.43) years. In the total one hundred patients, there were 37 patients of terlipressin induced hyponatremia. Majority of the patients were in the age group of (20 – 40) years and among these patients 17 presented Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia (37.78%). Another major age group was (41 – 60) years was observed in 55 patients; whereas, 20 presented Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia (36.37%).

Conclusion: The outcomes of this research reflect a higher occurrence of Terlipressin induced hyponatremia. No correlation was observed between age, gender and Terlipressin induced hyponatremia.

Key Words: Sodium Levels, Vasoactive Drugs, Upper GI Bleeding, Terlipressin and Hyponatremia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastro-oesophageal varices are persistently reported among 40% to 60% of the cirrhotic patients; the onset of bleeding occurs among 25% to 35% of the patients with 80% to 90% of bleeding episodes among such patients [1]. Variceal bleeding is commonly reported among the patients of portal hypertension which causes seventy percent episodes of the upper gastrointestinal bleeding along with an onset of liver cirrhosis [2, 3]. Thus, there is a need to identify variceal origin among the patients of cirrhosis presented with bleeding of acute upper gastrointestinal. Diagnosis can be made through emergency endoscopy along with indications of active varix bleeding (blood observed oozing or spurting by varix), varix adherent clot, white nipple and onset of varices in the absence of other potential bleeding sources [4].

Last decade has witnessed various advancements in the treatment of variceal bleeding. A number of guidelines have been produced for the management of evidence-based variceal bleeding patients in an effective way [5]. Pharmacological and Endoscopic treatment can control 70% to 80% of variceal bleeding episodes among patients [6]. Injection sclerotherapy and variceal ligation are among available endoscopic treatment modalities. Endoscopic sclerotherapy refers to halted variceal bleeding by bleeding varix thrombosis by intra-variceal or para-variceal sclerosant injection. Ethanolamine oleate and Sodium tetradecyl sulphate are repeatedly used sclerosants [7].

Terlipressin came as an alternative option which replaced vasopressin, which is only utilized for an unfavourable safety profile of the cirrhosis. Nowadays, it has been graded as standard management for the bleeding oesophageal varices in the regions where its availability has been made as being a vasoactive drug it can improve the rate of survival [8]. Terlipressin also causes hemodynamic effects due to its predominant effects on vasopressin-1 receptors as it is vasopressin receptor agonist. But it also shows affinity to vasopressin-2 receptors located in kidneys collecting duct and induce retention of the water through water canal aquaporin-2 insertion. Terlipressin induces natriuresis, improves renal function and reduces solute-free water excretion; these features explain the hyponatremia development [10]. According to Sola, 36% of patients presented the development of hyponatremia due to a decrease in the level of sodium after being managed by Terlipressin (> 10 mEq/L).

Active variceal bleeding refers to cherry red spots on varices, active blood from varices and duodenum on

endoscopy and no related source of haemorrhage in the stomach. Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia is positive with a level of sodium (≥ 10 mEq/L) in the course of Terlipressin therapy on 1st, 2nd and 3rd day; whereas, final outcomes were taken on the 3rd day of treatment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from July 2017 to March 2018 on a total of one hundred patients who were presented with acute variceal bleeding. All the patients were Hyponatremia induced Terlipressin were also examined. All the patients faced the onset of acute variceal bleeding because of portal hypertension who were in the age bracket of (20 – 60) years from both genders. We did not include all those patients who presented hepatocellular carcinoma, hyponatremia, hypothyroidism, nephritic syndrome, Addison disease, severe diarrhoea, renal failure, cardiovascular disease, levels of serum sodium (≤ 135 mEq/L), hypersensitive patients, pregnant patients and unwilling patients. Patients were assessed for clinical parameters along with physical examination and history. After taking initial resuscitative measures we started Terlipressin therapy in each patient through 2 mg/4 hrs dose for first twenty-four hours for three days and monitored the level of sodium. Sodium levels were measured twice a day for a possible decrease in the value (> 10 mEq/L) from its baseline. Study variables and patient's biodata was documented for every patient. SPSS software was used for quantitative and qualitative variables analysis (P-value ≤ 0.05).

RESULTS:

The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of (20 – 60) years and the mean age of these patients was (45.78 \pm 8.43) years. In the total one hundred patients, there were 37 patients of terlipressin induced hyponatremia. Majority of the patients were in the age group of (20 – 40) years and among these patients 17 presented Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia (37.78%). Another major age group was (41 – 60) years was observed in 55 patients; whereas, 20 presented Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia (36.37%). There was no significant statistical association between age and Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia (P-Value = 1.00). Among one hundred patients there were 58 male and 42 female patients. Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia was reported among 20 males out of 58 (34.48%); whereas, it was reported among 17 females out of 42 (40.48%). There was an insignificant correlation between Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia and gender (P-Value = 0.6751).

Table: Comparison of Age and Gender

Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia		Yes		No		P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Age	20 – 40 Years	17	37.78	28	62.22	0.000
	41 – 60 Years	20	36.37	35	63.63	
Gender	Male	20	34.48	38	65.52	0.6751
	Female	17	40.48	25	59.52	

DISCUSSION:

Acute variceal bleeding is commonly treated with Terlipressin. It is a synthetic vasopressin analogue which has prolonged half-life in comparison to vasopressin, reduced side-effects and it can effectively control acute variceal bleeding [11]. Terlipressin is managed as 2mg (IV injections) and 1mg in the time of 4 – 6 hours for two to five days. A study demonstrated the association of Terlipressin with reduction of relative risk up to 34% for mortality rates than the administration of placebo [11].

Terlipressin can potently improve survival by controlling bleeding rate among patients. It is only known drug which carries the potential to improve variceal bleeding induced mortality rates [12]. Terlipressin is equally effective for the treatment of disease severity like other modalities such as endoscopic injection sclerotherapy. It is safer than endoscopic injection sclerotherapy and nitroglycerin + vasopressin [13]. It has 75% to 80% efficacy rate to control acute variceal bleeding within forty-eight hours as demonstrated in various trials [13].

The patients were enrolled in the age bracket of (20 – 60) years and the mean age of these patients was (45.78 ± 8.43) years. In the total one hundred patients, there were 37 patients of terlipressin induced hyponatremia. Akhtar and Azam reported respective mean age of 45 and 47 years in their research studies which can be compared with the outcomes of our research. Whereas, Shaikh W reported a mean age of 41 years among one hundred patients. Past studies have shown a higher mean age which is more than fifty years than our reported mean age [1, 8, 9]. Among one hundred patients there were 58 male and 42 female patients. Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia was reported among 20 males out of 58 (34.48%); whereas, it was reported among 17 females out of 42 (40.48%). There was an insignificant correlation between Terlipressin induced Hyponatremia and gender (P-Value = 0.6751). The males were dominant over female population which is also reported in the past studies as females were dominated by males in the research population [14, 16].

According to Sola, after examining the Terlipressin effects on concentration of serum sodium among fifty-eight patients presented with acute portal-hypertensive bleeding there was a decrease in the level of sodium serum from (134.9 ± 6.6 to 130.5 ± 7.7) mEq/L (P-Value = 0.002) [10]. Sodium was reduced in blood among 67% patients; among these patient's a moderate decrease was reported in 31% patients (5 – 10 mEq/L) and marked decrease was reported in 36%

patients (> 10 mEq/L). Douriez E reported severe hyponatremia after repeated Terlipressin administration. Feu reported hyponatremia among 6.25% patients in the total of eighty acute variceal bleeding patients who were treated with Terlipressin [17]. According to Escorsell A, there were only four hyponatremia patients in the total of 105 patients who were treated with Terlipressin; whereas, no patient in the sclerotherapy group.

CONCLUSION:

The outcomes of this research reflect a higher occurrence of Terlipressin induced hyponatremia. No correlation was observed between age, gender and Terlipressin induced hyponatremia.

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